

Distinguishing active and legacy source contributions to stream water quality: Comparative quantification for chloride and metals

Georgia Destouni¹ | Zahra Kalantari^{1,2}

¹Department of Physical Geography, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden

²Department of Sustainable Development, Environmental Science and Engineering, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden

Correspondence

Georgia Destouni, Department of Physical Geography, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden.

Email: georgia.destouni@natgeo.su.se

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Abstract

Hydrochemical constituents in streams may originate from currently active sources at the surface and/or legacy sources from earlier surface inputs, waste deposits and land contamination. Distinction and quantification of these source contributions are needed for improved interpretation of tracer data and effective reduction of waterborne environmental pollutants. This article develops a methodology that recognizes and quantifies some general mechanistic differences in stream concentration and load behavior versus discharge between such source contributions. The methodology is applied to comparative analysis of stream concentration data for chloride (Cl^-), copper (Cu), lead (Pb), and zinc (Zn), and corresponding data for water discharge, measured over the period 1990–2018 in multiple hydrological catchments (19 for Cl^- , 11 for Cu and Zn, 10 for Pb) around the major Lake Mälaren in Sweden. For Cl^- , the average load fraction of active sources is quantified to be 19%, and the average active and legacy concentration contributions as 2.9 and 11 mg/L, respectively. For the metals, the average active load fractions at outlets are 1%–3% over all catchments and 9%–14% in the relatively few catchments with mixed metal sources. Average active and legacy concentration contributions are 0.14 and 3.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Cu, 0.05 and 1.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Pb, and 1.4 and 12 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Zn, respectively. This multi-catchment analysis thus indicates a widespread prevalence of legacy sources, with greater legacy than active concentration contributions for both Cl^- and the metals, and active contributions playing a greater role for chloride than for the metals. The relatively simple first-order methodology developed and applied in the study can be used to screen commonly available stream monitoring data for possible distinction of active and legacy contributions of any hydrochemical constituent in and across various hydrological catchment settings.

KEYWORDS

chloride, legacy sources, metals, multi-catchment analysis, source attribution, water quality

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1 | INTRODUCTION

Stream water quality depends on many factors, including multiple sources of various substances (e.g., tracers, pollutants) and different transport and biogeochemical processes acting on these along various waterborne pathways from source areas to receiving waters (Destouni et al., 2010; Santos et al., 2011). The sources may be partitioned into two distinct categories, as originating from currently active or legacy sources (Destouni & Jarsjö, 2018). Active sources are defined as those entering a hydrological catchment by infiltration and runoff at the surface. Hydrochemical constituents from active sources are transported relatively rapidly through the catchment to surface waters. In contrast, legacy sources reside in soils, slow groundwater, sediments from earlier active surface inputs, waste deposition, and land contamination. Hydrochemical constituents from legacy source stores are released into mobile water in the catchment and transported to surface waters over longer time scales (ERMITE-Consortium, Younger, & Wolkersdorfer, 2004; Santos et al., 2005; Wolkersdorfer & Bowell, 2005).

Long-lived legacies from earlier surface inputs can be expected due to both slow transport and various physical and biogeochemical mass transfer and transformation processes occurring along subsurface water pathways and delaying the arrival of sorptive and reactive pollutants to downgradient waters (Cvetkovic et al., 2012; Destouni & Graham, 1995). Physical slow transport and mass transfer processes may also affect conservative tracers like chloride (Bastviken et al., 2006; Bastviken et al., 2007; Grimaldi et al., 2009; Jobbagy & Jackson, 2007), and tracers considered as ideal, like stable water isotopes (Kendall & Caldwell, 1998; Kirchner et al., 2010). For reactive pollutants, such as metals from acid mine drainage (Eriksson & Destouni, 1997; Malmström et al., 2008) and contaminated land (Augustsson et al., 2016), various reaction processes determine the rates of net weathering, dissolution, and desorption along the transport pathways to streams. To accurately interpret water quality and choose effective measures for quality improvement, active and legacy source contributions need to be distinguished, and pollution mitigation measures chosen and placed so they can effectively target the different types of sources (Baresel et al., 2006).

This article addresses the need to quantitatively distinguish active and legacy sources of the hydrochemical constituents observed in streamflow, using commonly available stream monitoring data. We hypothesize on mechanistic grounds (Destouni et al., 2010; Eriksson & Destouni, 1997) that: (i) some general key differences exist and can be distinguished from the behavior of monitored concentration, load and water discharge data for tracers and pollutants that originate from active or legacy sources. We further hypothesize on both mechanistic and source-prevalence grounds that (ii) legacy source contributions may be dominant for substances like metals, and considerable, even though to likely lesser degree, for tracers like chloride. The basis for the second hypothesis is that pollutants like metals are reactive and may originate from early waste deposition and land contamination (Augustsson et al., 2016; Renberg et al., 2001; Wolkersdorfer & Bowell, 2005), while tracers like chloride may to greater degree

originate from active sources, such as wet and dry deposition, wastewater discharges, and uses of de-icing salt, fertilizers and manure (Dugan et al., 2017). To test these hypotheses, we develop a relatively simple, general source-distinction methodology, and apply this to source interpretation and quantification based on stream data for chloride (Cl^-) and the metals copper (Cu), lead (Pb) and zinc (Zn) monitored in multiple hydrological catchments around the major Swedish Lake Mälaren (Sweden's third-largest freshwater lake with its water quality being essential for water security in the most densely populated region of Sweden) over the time period 1990–2018.

2 | METHODS AND DATA

2.1 | Comparative source distinction methodology

We developed a methodology for identifying and quantifying some key mechanistic characteristics that may generally differ and, as such, can be used for a first approximate distinction between currently active and legacy source contributions to monitored stream water quality. The aim here is a relatively simple general quantification, rather than specifically modeling all possible sources, and transport, mass transfer, transformation and reaction processes that a waterborne substance may be subject to under various site conditions.

For such first-order quantification, we consider a mixture of active and legacy sources of tracer/pollutant spread over a catchment. The active sources maintain a relatively stable average tracer/pollutant input rate (I_{in-A} , units of mass per time) with water infiltration or runoff at the surface. Additionally, legacy sources in soil, slow groundwater, sediments over the catchment release tracer/pollutant into the mobile water flow through the catchment at some relatively stable average release rate (k , units of released mass fraction per time). In combination, the active and legacy sources contribute load fractions $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$ (dimensionless) and $1-\gamma$ to total load L_{out-M} at the catchment outlet, respectively, with corresponding absolute load contributions $L_{out-A} = \gamma L_{out-M}$ and $L_{out-L} = (1-\gamma) L_{out-M}$. For such mixed source conditions, the following first-order mechanistic expression may be used to represent total tracer/pollutant load L_{out-M} at the catchment outlet:

$$L_{out-M} = L_{out-L} + L_{out-A} \approx \left(\frac{C_0^*}{n} kT \right) Q_{out} + \alpha_A I_{in-A} \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), Q_{out} is the water discharge corresponding to and carrying the load L_{out-M} at and through the catchment outlet. Furthermore, for the active sources, $0 \leq \alpha_A \leq 1$ (dimensionless) is the average tracer/pollutant fraction delivered from the stable active input rate I_{in-A} to catchment outlet (Levi et al., 2018). For the legacy sources (Eriksson & Destouni, 1997), C_0^* is the average bulk tracer/pollutant concentration (average tracer/pollutant mass per unit bulk soil/aquifer/sediment volume) at the start of the study period, n is the average volumetric water content (porosity for largely saturated conditions; dimensionless), and T is the average turnover time (average advective

transport time) of mobile water flowing through the catchment and its diffuse legacy sources to the outlet.

With average l_{in-A} applying to active source conditions over the catchment surface, average k , C_0^* , and n applying to diffuse legacy source conditions over the whole catchment, and average T and α_A applying to water flow and tracer/pollutant transport processes that also occur over the whole catchment and over long time, all of these quantities may be relatively independent of output discharge Q_{out} at a specific time and monitoring point (catchment outlet). As such, Equation (1) thus expresses a possible approximate linear relationship between specific tracer/pollutant load L_{out-M} and corresponding specific discharge Q_{out} , which may represent a possible data-given best-fit regression line (purple line in Figure 1) for measured data of these variables over time at catchment outlet. This hypothesis is motivated by L - Q regression linearity seen in previous studies for different waterborne substances (Basu et al., 2010; Destouni & Jarsjö, 2018) and is tested here directly against monitoring data for chloride and metals in multiple catchments.

For a regression line L - Q with positive intercept (Int), Equation (1) implies that the data-given $Int > 0$ directly determines the active source contribution L_{out-A} as:

$$L_{out-A} = \alpha_A l_{in-A} = C_{out-A} Q_{out} \quad (2)$$

where C_{out-A} is, by definition, the associated flux-averaged tracer/pollutant concentration (Cvetkovic & Dagan, 1994; Kreft & Zuber, 1978). The intercept Int quantifies thereby also the active load fraction as $\gamma = Int/L_{out-M}$, and implies mixed or only active source contributions for $0 < \gamma < 1$ and $\gamma = 1$ (purple and green lines in Figure 1), respectively. Conservation of mass for stable average l_{in-A} and α_A implies that the corresponding average load L_{out-A} must also be stable, leading to chemodynamic concentration behaviour (Basu et al., 2010). That is, monitored concentration C_{out-A} varies then with Q_{out} such that L_{out-A} fulfils mass continuity and remains stable on average,

while individual daily/monthly/annual data points of L_{out-A} still vary around that average level (Cvetkovic et al., 2012).

For a regression line L - Q with positive slope (Sl), Equation (1) implies that the legacy source contribution L_{out-L} is:

$$L_{out-L} = \left(\frac{C_0^*}{n}\right) kT (Q_{out} - Q_{out-Lt}) = C_{out-L} (Q_{out} - Q_{out-Lt}) \quad \text{for } Q_{out} - Q_{out-Lt} \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

with Sl determining the associated flux-averaged concentration $C_{out-L} = Sl$. If the line intercept $Int \leq 0$, there is no active load contribution and thus only legacy sources contribute to $L_{out-M} = L_{out-L}$ at catchment outlet ($\gamma = 0$, $1-\gamma = 1$), for average discharge exceeding some minimum threshold value $Q_{out} \geq Q_{out-Lt} = -Int/Sl$, below which $L_{out-L} = 0$ (see brown and blue lines in Figure 1 for $Q_{out-Lt} = 0$ and $Q_{out-Lt} > 0$, respectively). Equation (3) is based on zeroth-order release kinetics $C^* = C_0^*(1-kt)$ and applies over a stable period of time $T \leq t \leq 1/k$ after start of the whole study period at $t = 0$ (Eriksson & Destouni, 1997). At $t = T$, all mobile water in the catchment at $t = 0$ has been turned over once, and all water reaching the outlet thereafter from any given point within the catchment will have received a similar tracer/pollutant amount from the legacy source release. The stable period ends at $t = 1/k$ when the legacy source (C_0^*) is fully depleted, as implied by the relative rate k for the zeroth-order release condition; after $t = 1/k$, the output concentration C_{out-L} will be decreasing and become zero at $t = 1/k + T$ (Eriksson & Destouni, 1997). During $T \leq t \leq 1/k$, a data-given L - Q regression line with positive slope Sl and near-zero or negative intercept Int (brown and blue lines in Figure 1) implies chemostatic behaviour (Basu et al., 2010) with stable average C_{out-L} for only legacy load contributions to catchment outlet.

In summary, Equations (1)–(3) quantify possible L - Q regression line types for various relative active and legacy source contributions, and highlight some general key differences that may emerge from data for

FIGURE 1 Schematic illustration of different possible types of regression lines expressed by Equations (1)–(3) for tracer or pollutant load versus water discharge data

tracer/pollutant contributions originating from one or the other of these source types. These contributions, with fractions γ for active and $(1-\gamma)$ for legacy sources, can thereby be quantified from possible best-fit linear L-Q regression behavior emerging from commonly available stream monitoring data. This quantification is consistent and allows for direct result comparison between different tracers and pollutants, using the coefficient of determination (R^2) as performance measure of the data-given linear goodness of fit. In the present case study, linear regression and R^2 results, and associated concentration and γ values are evaluated for Cl^- , Cu, Pb, and Zn using monitoring data from multiple hydrological catchments around the Swedish Lake Mälaren.

2.2 | Case study area and data

For concrete data-based testing and quantification of the general source distinction Equations (1)–(3), we use official Swedish stream concentration data for Cl^- , Cu, Pb, and Zn, and associated water discharges monitored in multiple hydrological catchments around the major Swedish Lake Mälaren over the time period 1990–2018. The left map panel in Figure 2 shows the location within Sweden of the main Norrström hydrological catchment (red outline), which contains these multiple (sub)catchments that drain into Lake Mälaren and through that further into the Baltic Sea. The enlarged Norrström catchment map panels center and right in Figure 2 show the monitoring stations (red dots) for the Cl^- , Cu, Pb, and Zn data and their associated (sub)catchments (colored, with official station numbers also given; see further the Data Availability Statement below for links to data sources).

The Norrström catchment has an area of around 22 600 km² and a total population of around 2 million people. The catchment includes the capital Stockholm (the largest Swedish city) and its wider metropolitan area as well as the fourth, fifth and sixth-largest cities of Sweden (Uppsala, Västerås, Örebro, respectively; see map left in Figure 2). For the study period 1990–2018, the possible Cl^- , Cu, Pb, and Zn contributions to stream water quality by drainage from these urban areas are to large degree unmonitored (within the gray parts of the main Norrström catchment, center and right panels in Figure 2). One exception is a small catchment with Cl^- monitoring (number 36394 for Cl^- , Figure 2) in the most densely populated and oldest urban parts of Stockholm region (e.g., with Södertälje receiving city privileges in the 1300s; Gelotte, 2011) in the south-east of the main Norrström catchment. Other urban area exceptions are parts with various Cl^- , Cu, Pb, and Zn monitoring that include Uppsala in the north-east and Örebro in the south-west of the Norrström catchment.

With an area of 1074 km², Lake Mälaren is Sweden's third-largest freshwater lake and its water quality is essential for water security in this most densely populated region of Sweden. The Norrström catchment also includes Sweden's fourth-largest lake (Hjälmaren, Figure 2) and the region around these lakes has undergone rapid urbanization and industrialization. Agriculture and farming are also still present in this part of the Swedish fertile belt, except in the relatively more elevated and hilly northwestern part of the catchment, which is largely covered by mixed forest. Overall, the Norrström catchment has average annual temperature of 6.2°C (Elmhagen et al., 2015), precipitation of 630 mm/year and runoff of 230 mm/year, and comprises around 4% built-up areas, 36% agricultural and open land, 49% forest (mostly in the north-west of the basin), 1.5% wetlands and 9.5%

FIGURE 2 The location of Norrström catchment (red outline, left) and monitored (sub)catchments within it (colored, center and right) for chloride (Cl^-), copper (Cu), lead (Pb) and zinc (Zn)

inland waters, including the large lakes Mälaren and Hjälmaren (Darracq, 2007).

Possible sources of Cl^- include wet deposition with precipitation, dry deposition, wastewater discharges, and human uses of de-icing salt, fertilizers and manure (Dugan et al., 2017). A study of Cl^- sources in a north-central sub-catchment (number 727, map for Cl^- , Figure 2) reports that use of deicing salt accounts for 61% of the total Cl^- load to that stream, followed by fertilizers and manure (14%), infiltration and recharge from surface deposition (13%), dustbinding in gravel roads (7%), municipal and private sewage and discharges from wastewater treatment plants (4%), and leakage from landfills and other minor sources (1%) (Thunqvist, 2004). Furthermore, metals may originate from weathering of bedrock as well as airborne deposition at the surface and waterborne spreading from various anthropogenic sources in this region (Olli & Destouni, 2008). For example, Stockholm and the other main cities in this catchment have existed since hundreds of years, with much soil becoming polluted by industry, waste deposits, sewage, traffic, constructions, accidents, and so forth. (Asstrup & Thunholm, 2001; Linde et al., 2001). There is also a long history of metal mining in Sweden and this region, starting from around 3000 B.P. with numerous small furnaces used for household production of bronze and iron and with the raw material for this also containing other metals, such as Cu, Zn, and Pb (Hjärtner-Holdar, 1993). From around 1300 A.D. Swedish mining industry started to progress in full speed, leading to early increase of metal pollution in the sediments of Lake Mälaren from such intensified mining and metal processing, in particular in Bergslagen, a main mining district west and north of Lake Mälaren (Renberg et al., 2001). Numerous

abandoned mine wastes have accumulated and remain unremediated since then, from both pre-industrial and industrial mining in this district (Wolkersdorfer & Howell, 2005).

In the following, we use Equations (1)–(3) to distinguish and quantify the possible contributions to stream water quality of the various active and legacy types of sources of Cl^- , Cu, Pb, and Zn in the monitored (sub)catchments around Lake Mälaren (Figure 2). This is done from the parameters (intercept, slope) of the data-based L-Q regression lines for each studied substance and its monitored catchments (Figure 2). The L-Q regression line parameters characterize the source contributions in a catchment as: mixed for positive intercept and slope (implying active load fractions $0 < \gamma < 1$; purple line in Figure 1); only active, for positive intercept and near-zero slope (implying $\gamma \approx 1$, green line in Figure 1); or only legacy, for zero or negative intercept and positive slope (implying $\gamma \approx 0$, brown or blue lines in Figure 1).

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Result statistics

Figure 3(a) summarizes the goodness of fit, in terms of the coefficient of determination R^2 , of the data-given L-Q regression lines for Cl^- , Cu, Pb, and Zn in their respective monitored catchments around Lake Mälaren (Figure 2). The linear fits are overall good, with R^2 values greater than 0.5 for most catchments and average R^2 around 0.7–0.9 for both chloride and the metals. The highest R^2 values emerge for Cl^- and Cu, with R^2 somewhat lower and more variable for Pb and Zn

FIGURE 3 Resulting multi-catchment statistics of (a) coefficient of determination R^2 for best-fit regression line to chloride or metal load versus water discharge data, and (b) catchment area for all, the legacy, and the mixed catchments. Box plots in (a) and error bars of ± 1 standard deviation in (b) regard variability among the catchments in each category

(Figure 3(a)). Based on the mostly well-fit L - Q regression lines, the monitored catchments are characterized as having mixed ($0 < \gamma < 1$), or only active ($\gamma \approx 1$) or legacy ($\gamma \approx 0$) source contributions for Cl^- , Cu, Pb, and Zn at the catchment outlets. Figure 3(b) summarizes the results of this characterization, in terms of the number (red), area-share (blue), and absolute area statistics (averages ± 1 standard deviation) of catchments emerging to be in each source category. No catchment exhibits L - Q behavior characteristic of only active source contributions for any of the investigated substances. For Cl^- , most catchments (18 of total 19, with 99% area share) emerge as having mixed source contributions and only one catchment (with 1% area share) is characterized as dominated by legacy sources. The opposite applies to the metals, for which most catchments are characterized as legacy-dominated (8 of 11, 69% area for Cu; 9 of 10, 99.5% area for Pb; 9 of 11, 79% area for Zn) and only a few as mixed (the remaining 3, 1 and 2 catchments with area shares 31%, 0.5%, and 21% for Cu, Pb, and Zn, respectively).

Overall, the mixed catchments tend to be on average somewhat larger than the legacy-dominated catchments, even though small mixed catchments can also be found (e.g., a single small mixed catchment for Pb; Figure 3(b)). Figure 4(a) shows that the mixed catchments also tend to be somewhat wetter than the legacy catchments in terms of runoff (discharge per area). A larger catchment area may comprise a greater variation of sources and generates more absolute total discharge for the same runoff (discharge per area). The combination with area-specific runoff also tending to be greater in the area-wise somewhat larger mixed catchments may drive faster waterborne tracer/pollutant spreading that contributes to the more notable active load

contributions in these catchments, in particular for metals with otherwise dominant legacy contributions in most catchments (Figure 4(b)). For the legacy catchments, the data-given quantification of threshold discharge $Q_{\text{out-Lt}}$ (see blue line in Figure 1) shows that the corresponding average runoff value ($Q_{\text{out-Lt}}$ per catchment area) is overall much smaller than the actual average annual runoff in these catchments and the whole region (Figure 4(a)). This result is consistent with the identification of so many legacy-dominated catchments, the contributions of which would otherwise be expected to be relatively small for large threshold discharge $Q_{\text{out-Lt}}$ values.

The resulting values of active load fraction γ (Figure 4(b)) further show that it is on average 0.19 for Cl^- over all catchments, which are mostly mixed-source ones for Cl^- , and slightly greater at 0.21 over the many mixed catchments. For the metals, average γ is around 0.01–0.03 over all catchments, which are mostly legacy ones and thus have $\gamma \approx 0$, while average γ over the few mixed catchments for metals is around 0.09–0.14. Corresponding concentration results (Figure 5) show that, for Cl^- , the active and legacy concentration contributions at outlet, $C_{\text{out-A}}$ and $C_{\text{out-L}}$, are on average around 2.9 and 10.8 mg/L, respectively. The average values of $C_{\text{out-A}}$ and $C_{\text{out-L}}$ for metals are 0.14 and 3.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Cu, 0.05 and 1.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Pb, and 1.4 and 12 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Zn. These results indicate widespread prevalence of contributing legacy sources, with overall greater concentration contributions at catchment outlets than from the active sources for both Cl^- and the metals. Even though legacy source contributions are dominant, active source contributions are also distinguished and play a much greater role for chloride than for the metals.

FIGURE 4 Resulting multi-catchment statistics of temporally average (a) runoff and (b) active load fraction γ for all and for the mixed catchments. Error bars show ± 1 standard deviation among the catchments in each category

3.2 | Result mapping and spatial analysis

Figure 6 maps the results for concentration contributions of legacy sources, along with the associated legacy load fractions $1-\gamma$ over the Norrström catchment, while Figure 7 maps corresponding results for active source contributions. For Cl^- , a small monitored catchment (number 36394 for Cl^- , Figure 2) in the most densely populated and old urban parts of Stockholm region, south-east in the main Norrström catchment, emerges as a major legacy hotspot with an average concentration contribution of 80 mg/L. This exceeds average concentrations in the other

monitored catchments (Figure 6) and is order of magnitude greater than most average active contributions (Figure 7). Besides this small monitored urban catchment around Stockholm, the other two monitored urban areas of Uppsala in the north-east and Örebro in the south-west parts of the Norrström catchment emerge as the next-largest legacy contributors of Cl^- , with average concentration values around 12–13 mg/L (Figure 5). The north-east (sub)catchment that includes Uppsala also has a high average active concentration of 25 mg/L while the south-west catchment that includes Örebro has a relatively small average active concentration of just 0.3 mg/L. With the Stockholm region being mostly unmonitored, but still

FIGURE 5 Resulting multi-catchment statistics of temporal average legacy and active concentration contributions at outlet in all catchments and in the mixed catchments, respectively. Error bars show ± 1 standard deviation among the catchments in each category

FIGURE 6 Spatial distribution of temporal average legacy concentration contributions and associated average load fractions $1-\gamma$

FIGURE 7 Spatial distribution of temporal average active concentration contributions and associated average load fractions γ

indicated as a major legacy area by its single small monitored hotspot catchment, we do not know if the overall Stockholm concentration pattern may show larger (as for Uppsala) or smaller (as for Örebro) active than legacy concentrations. Further monitoring and research efforts are called for to resolve this important question for regional water quality.

The legacy hotspot patterns are similar among the metals, but different from the chloride pattern. The metal-contributing catchments are mostly legacy ones, located in the old mining areas north-west and north of Lake Mälaren (Renberg et al., 2001). A north-central catchment emerges as a major legacy hotspot with average concentrations of 6 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Pb, 34 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Zn, and 4 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Cu (Figure 6). This catchment includes the important mining area of Sala, which has a mining industry dating back to the 11th century for silver and lead production from sulfide ores with a lead content of 50%–70% and a silver content of 2%–4% (Brännvall et al., 1999). The major Bergslagen mining district in the north-west, and the north-east catchments that also include some major old mining sites (Renberg et al., 2001) also have relatively high average legacy concentrations of metals, of around 1.5–1.6 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Pb, 14–15 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Zn, and 4–5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for Cu (Figure 6). The few mixed-source catchments for metals are also found in these north-west and north-east areas (Figure 7), but with much smaller average active than legacy concentrations.

4 | DISCUSSION

The chloride catchments emerge as mostly mixed from the present source attribution. This is consistent with the variety of

contributing sources reported for Cl^- in this region (Thunqvist, 2004), as in other parts of the world (Daley et al., 2009; Dugan et al., 2017; Kaushal et al., 2005; Panno et al., 2006). The Cl^- concentration mapping indicates urban areas as hotspots of both active and legacy sources. This is consistent with high levels and increasing trends of freshwater salinization (Chapra et al., 2012) that are correlated with impervious surface area (Kaushal et al., 2005) and urbanization (Daley et al., 2009) also in other parts of the world. The legacy source contributions of Cl^- to streams, however, are still dominant. Both past and current urban uses of de-icing salt, along with urban storm water runoff and wastewater discharges may thus contribute to the urban legacy and active source contributions of Cl^- . In this fertile belt of Sweden, the urban centers are also surrounded by historic and current agricultural and farming areas, with uses of fertilizers and manure in these adding to the urban active and legacy sources of Cl^- in this region.

For the metals, most catchments emerge as legacy-dominated, implying that the Cu, Pb, and Zn concentrations found in the streams of the Norrström catchment may largely originate from the old mine waste deposits in this region. This implication is supported by the mapped spatial distribution of the legacy concentrations of metals, which is consistent with the locations of old mining sites and abandoned mine wastes from both pre-industrial and industrial time in this region, including the major Bergslagen mining district. In general, this implication is also consistent with persisting metal impacts from historic mining reported also from other parts of the world (Baron et al., 2006; Beane et al., 2016; Byrne et al., 2012; Camizuli et al., 2021; Resongles et al., 2014).

In general, source attribution mapping can identify hotspots of active and legacy sources, and relate them to indicators of current and earlier human activity. For example, population density and various land uses, waste deposits, and contaminated land areas are such activity indicators. Such source identification is needed for selecting and locating effective mitigation measures for the different source types. For active sources, relevant measures may be, for example, regulations and incentives for improved collection and treatment of urban storm water and industrial wastewater. For legacy sources in soil, groundwater and sediments, other types of measures are needed, such as contaminated land remediation, and restoration and construction of wetlands for enhanced pollutant retention.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

Quantitative distinction of active and legacy source contributions is needed for improved interpretation of tracer data and effective mitigation of waterborne environmental pollutants. The relatively simple first-order methodology developed in this study recognizes some general mechanistic differences in the stream water quality behavior of hydrochemical components contributed by these source types. This behavior difference can be used to screen commonly available stream monitoring data for possible distinction of active and legacy source contributions of any hydrochemical constituent in and across various hydrological catchment settings.

The application of this methodology to the present multi-catchment analysis indicates widespread prevalence of legacy sources, with overall greater legacy than active contributions for both chloride and metals. For chloride, urban areas are indicated as hotspots of both active and legacy sources. For metals, old mining activities and their abandoned mine wastes are indicated as legacy hotspots.

More research is needed on such source distinction and identification of hotspots, and their relationships to current and historic human activities for various tracers and pollutants in different parts of the world. As a basis for this, hydrochemical monitoring needs to be better coordinated and enhanced, to detect the legacy sources in addition to the more well-known active sources and effectively target relevant mitigation measures for each source type.

The key difference between active and legacy component behavior in stream water quality regards the dependence on water discharge. Monitoring data therefore need to represent the same hydrological catchments and extend over the same time periods with continuous data availability for both concentrations and water discharges. The water discharge dependence on hydro-climatic variability and change also implies different climate sensitivity for tracer and pollutant components from legacy and active sources. Further research is needed to better understand and be able to project the implications of these climate-sensitivity differences for future water quality.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The concentration data used in this study are available from the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), Department of Water and Environment, Data host for inland waters, <https://www.slu.se/institutioner/vatten-miljo/datavardskap/>. The data for water discharges are available from the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI), <https://vattenwebb.smhi.se/nadia/>. Catchment delineations are based on data from SMHI, <https://www.smhi.se/data/hydrologi/sjoar-och-vattendrag/ladda-ner-data-fran-svenskt-vattenarkiv-1.20127>.

ORCID

Georgia Destouni <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9408-4425>

Jacopo Cantoni <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7611-5758>

REFERENCES

- Aastrup, M., & Thunholm, B. (2001). Heavy metals in Stockholm groundwater - concentrations and fluxes. *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution: Focus*, 1, 25–41. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1017535601625>.
- Augustsson, A., Uddh Söderberg, T., Jarsjö, J., Åström, M., Olofsson, B., Balfors, B., & Destouni, G. (2016). The risk of overestimating the risk-metal leaching to groundwater near contaminated glass waste deposits and exposure via drinking water. *Science of the Total Environment*, 566–567, 1420–1431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.06.003>
- Baresel, C., Destouni, G., & Gren, I. M. (2006). The influence of metal source uncertainty on cost-effective allocation of mine water pollution abatement in catchments. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 78(2), 138–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2005.03.013>
- Baron, S., Carignan, J., & Ploquin, A. (2006). Dispersion of heavy metals (metalloids) in soils from 800-year-old pollution (Mont-Lozère, France). *Environmental Science & Technology*, 40(17), 5319–5326. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es0606430>
- Bastviken, D., Sandén, P., Svensson, T., Ståhlberg, A. C., Magounakis, M., & Öberg, G. (2006). Chloride retention and release in a boreal forest soil: Effects of soil water residence time and nitrogen and chloride loads. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 40, 2977–2982. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es0523237>
- Bastviken, D., Thomsen, F., Svensson, T., Karlsson, S., Sandén, P., Shaw, G., Matucha, M., & Öberg, G. (2007). Chloride retention in forest soil by microbial uptake and by natural chlorination of organic matter. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 71, 3182–3192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gca.2007.04.028>
- Basu, N. B., Destouni, G., Jawitz, J. W., Thompson, S. E., Loukinova, N. V., Darracq, A., Zanardo, S., Yaeger, M., Sivapalan, M., Rinaldo, A., & Rao, P. S. C. (2010). Nutrient loads exported from managed catchments reveal emergent biogeochemical stationarity. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 37(23), L23404. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010GL045168>
- Beane, S. J., Comber, S. D. W., Rieuwerts, J., & Long, P. (2016). Abandoned metal mines and their impact on receiving waters: A case study from Southwest England. *Chemosphere*, 153, 294–306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2016.03.022>

- Brännvall, M.-L., Bindler, R., Renberg, I., Emteryd, O., Bartnicki, J., & Billström, K. (1999). The Medieval metal industry was the cradle of modern large-scale atmospheric lead pollution in northern Europe. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 33, 4391–4395. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es990279n>
- Byrne, P., Wood, P. J., & Reid, I. (2012). The impairment of river systems by metal mine contamination: A review including remediation options. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*, 42, 2017–2077. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10643389.2011.574103>
- Camizuli, E., Rossi, M., & Gasquet, D. (2021). Trace metals dispersion from 1000 years of mining activity in the northern French Alps. *The Extractive Industries and Society*, 8, 135–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.exis.2020.08.017>
- Chapra, S. C., Dove, A., & Warren, D. J. (2012). Long-term trends of Great Lakes major ion chemistry. *Journal of Great Lakes Research*, 38, 550–560. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jglr.2012.06.010>
- Cvetkovic, V., Carstens, C., Selroos, J.-O., & Destouni, G. (2012). Water and solute transport along hydrological pathways. *Water Resources Research*, 48(6), W06537. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011WR011367>
- Cvetkovic, V., & Dagan, G. (1994). Transport of kinetically sorbing solute by steady random velocity in heterogeneous porous formations. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 65, 189–215. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112094000807>
- Daley, M. L., Potter, J. D., & McDowell, W. H. (2009). Salinization of urbanizing New Hampshire streams and groundwater: Effects of road salt and hydrologic variability. *Journal of the North American Benthological Society*, 28(4), 929–940. <https://doi.org/10.1899/09-052.1>
- Darracq, A. (2007). *Long-term development, modeling and management of nutrient loading to inland and coastal waters* (Doctoral dissertation). Department of Physical Geography and Quaternary Geology, Stockholm University, Stockholm. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A197657>
- Destouni, G., & Graham, W. D. (1995). Solute transport through an integrated heterogeneous soil-groundwater system. *Water Resources Research*, 31(8), 1935–1944. <https://doi.org/10.1029/95WR01330>
- Destouni, G., & Jarsjö, J. (2018). Zones of untreatable water pollution call for better appreciation of mitigation limits and opportunities. *WIREs Water*, 5(6), e1312. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wat2.1312>
- Destouni, G., Persson, K., Prieto, C., & Jarsjö, J. (2010). General quantification of catchment-scale nutrient and pollutant transport through the subsurface to surface and coastal waters. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 44, 2048–2055. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es902338y>
- Dugan, H. E., Summers, J. C., Skaff, N. K., Krivak-Tetley, F. E., Doubek, J. P., Burke, S. M., Bartlett, S. L., Arvola, L., Jarjanazi, H., Korponai, J., Kleeberg, A., Monet, G., Monteith, D., Moore, K., Rogora, M., Hanson, P. C., & Weathers, K. C. (2017). Long-term chloride concentrations in North American and European freshwater lakes. *Scientific Data*, 4, 170101. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2017.101>
- Elmhagen, B., Destouni, G., Angerbjörn, A., Borgström, S., Boyd, E., Cousins, S. A. O., Dalén, L., Ehrlén, J., Ermold, M., Hambäck, P. A., Hedlund, J., Hylander, K., Jaramillo, F., Lagerholm, V. K., Lyon, S. W., Moor, H., Nykvist, B., Pasanen-Mortensen, M., Plue, J., ... Lindborg, R. (2015). Interacting effects of change in climate, human population, land use, and water use on biodiversity and ecosystem services. *Ecology and Society*, 20(1), 23. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-07145-200123>
- Eriksson, N., & Destouni, G. (1997). Combined effects of dissolution kinetics, secondary mineral precipitation, and preferential flow on copper leaching from mining waste rock. *Water Resources Research*, 33(3), 471–483. <https://doi.org/10.1029/96WR03466>
- ERMITE-Consortium, Younger, P. L., & Wolkersdorfer, C. (2004). Mining impacts on the fresh water environment: Technical and managerial guidelines for catchment scale management. *Mine Water and the Environment*, 23, 1–80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10230-004-0028-0>
- Gelotte, G. (2011). *Södertäljes historia*, Södertälje kommun, Trosa. <https://destinationsodertalje.se/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/sodertaljes-historia-sv.pdf>
- Grimaldi, C., Thomas, Z., Fossey, M., Fauvel, Y., & Merot, P. (2009). High chloride concentrations in the soil and groundwater under an oak hedge in the West of France: An indicator of evapotranspiration and water movement. *Hydrological Processes*, 23, 1865–1873. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.7316>
- Hjärtner-Holdar, E. (1993). *Järnets och metallurgins introduktion i Sverige. The introduction of iron and iron metallurgy to Sweden* (Dissertation). Department of Archaeology, Uppsala University, Uppsala, 206.
- Jobby, E. G., & Jackson, R. B. (2007). Groundwater and soil chemical changes under phreatophytic tree plantations. *Journal of Geophysical Research Biogeosciences*, 112, G02013. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006JG000246>
- Kaushal, S. S., Groffman, P. M., Likens, G. E., Belt, K. T., Stack, W. P., Kelly, V. R., Band, L. E., & Fisher, G. T. (2005). From The Cover: Increased salinization of fresh water in the northeastern United States. *PNAS*, 102(38), 13517–13520. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0506414102>
- Kendall, C., & Caldwell, E. A. (1998). Fundamentals of isotope geochemistry. In C. Kendall & J. J. McDonnell (Eds.), *Isotope tracers in catchment hydrology* (pp. 51–86). Elsevier.
- Kirchner, J. W., Tetzlaff, D., & Soulsby, C. (2010). Comparing chloride and water isotopes as hydrological tracers in two Scottish catchments. *Hydrological Processes*, 24, 1631–1645. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.7676>
- Kreft, A., & Zuber, A. (1978). On the physical meaning of the dispersion equation and its solutions for different initial and boundary conditions. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 33, 1471–1480. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2509\(78\)85196-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2509(78)85196-3)
- Levi, L., Cvetkovic, V., & Destouni, G. (2018). Data-driven analysis of nutrient inputs and transfers through nested catchments. *Science of the Total Environment*, 610–611, 482–494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.08.003>
- Linde, M., Bengtsson, H., & Öborn, I. (2001). Concentrations and pools of heavy metals in urban soils in Stockholm, Sweden. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution: Focus*, 1(3–4), 83–101. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1017599920280>
- Malmström, M. E., Berglund, S., & Jarsjö, J. (2008). Combined effects of spatially variable flow and mineralogy on the attenuation of acid mine drainage in groundwater. *Applied Geochemistry*, 23(6), 1419–1436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeochem.2007.12.029>
- Olli, G., & Destouni, G. (2008). Long-term heavy metal loading to near-shore lake sediments. *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution*, 192, 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-008-9638-7>
- Panno, S. V., Hackley, K. C., Hwang, H. H., Greenberg, S. E., Krapac, I. G., Landsberger, S., & O'Kelly, D. J. (2006). Characterization and identification of Na-Cl sources in ground water. *Ground Water*, 44, 176–187. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6584.2005.00127.x>
- Renberg, I., Bindler, R., Bradshaw, E., Emteryd, O., & McGowan, S. (2001). Sediment Evidence of Early Eutrophication and Heavy Metal Pollution of Lake Mälaren, Central Sweden. *Ambio*, 30(8), 496–502. <https://doi.org/10.1579/0044-7447-30.8.496>
- Resongles, E., Casiot, C., Freyrier, R., Dezileau, L., Viers, J., & Elbaz-Poulichet, F. (2014). Persisting impact of historical mining activity to metal (Pb, Zn, Cd, Ti, Hg) and metalloid (As, Sb) enrichment in sediments of the Gardon River, Southern France. *Environment*, 481, 509–521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.02.078>
- Santos, I. R., de Weys, J., & Eyre, B. D. (2011). Groundwater or floodwater? Assessing the pathways of metal exports from a coastal acid sulfate soil catchment. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 45(22), 9641–9648. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es202581h>
- Santos, I. R., Silva-Filho, E. V., Schaefer, C. E. G. R., Albuquerque-Filho, M. R., & Campos, L. S. (2005). Heavy metal contamination in coastal sediments and soils near the Brazilian Antarctic Station, King

- George Island. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 50(2), 185–194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2004.10.009>
- Thunqvist, E.-L. (2004). Regional increase of mean chloride concentration in water due to the application of deicing salt. *Science of the Total Environment*, 325(1–3), 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2003.11.020>
- Wolkersdorfer, C., & Howell, R. (2005). Contemporary reviews of mine water studies in Europe part 2. *Mine Water and the Environment*, 24(1), 2–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10230-005-0068-0>

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